

Diptera

- p.1 01 oldest fossil fly_Permotipula patricia, Permian_01
- p.2 02 generalized Diptera wing_02
- p.3 03 Diptera FW base, terminology_03
- p.4 04 Tabanidae, Tabanus atratus female FW base copy
- p.5 Asilidae, Diognites rubescens FW base_08
- p.6 Tabanidae, Tabanus atratus female FW base, B & W_05
- p.7 Tabanidae, Tabanus atratus female FW base_01
- p.8 Tabanidae, Tabanus atratus female FW base_04
- p.9 Tipulidae, Holorusia rubiginosa_06
- p.10 Tipulidae, holorusia rubifginosa FW base details_07

OLDEST FOSSIL FLY

Permotipula patricia Tillyard, Upper Permian, N.S.W., Australia

(some of Tillyard's veinal symbols changed here)

GENERALIZED FLY WING, with evolutionary (homologous Pterygote) veinal symbols

(based mainly on Syrphidae: *Cynorhinelia* sp.)

Fly venation is rather close to Mecoptera: Choristidae

TYOLOGICAL AND HOMOLOGOUS TERMS
 Diptera: Tabanidae, *Tabanus atratus* female, forewing

Tabanidae: *Tabanus atratus* female, FW

Tabanid wing articulation is close to the Diptera groundplan and provides interpretive clues. Note a mix of highly derived and plesiomorphic characters: 1Ax shows its composition of 4 sclerites, the posterior wing process is not fused to tergum (plesiomorphy), but the anal veins are unusually grouped together, and basal posterior margin bears 4 unique lobes.

Diptera: Tipulidae, *Tipula* sp.

Diptera: *Tabanidae* sp.
Fore wing

Tabanus atratus
classical articulation

FW Tabanidae: *Tabanus atratus* ♀

Note that all sclerites are separate from tergum (plesiomorphy).

Note that in Paleoptera, all proxalaria (PR) are fully separated from the tergum

! =tergum and wing organ have always been separate structures !

FW Tabanidae: *Tabanus atratus* ♀ (three-dimensional details)

AA 3+4

Tipulidae: *Holorusia rubiginosa*

Nematocera: Tipulidae: *Holorusia rubiginosa*

